

Technical report no. 2021–E
preliminary version

Addenda to “Mereosemiotics: Parts and signs”

Date: 23rd August 2021

Author: Horsch, M. T.

Funding information:

- DFG, NFDI4Cat, project no. 441926934

Accessibility:

- doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5236732
- <https://zenodo.org/communities/inprodat/>

Addenda to “Mereosemiotics: Parts and signs”

Inprodat e.V. technical report 2021-E

Martin Thomas Horsch

*UK Research and Innovation, STFC Daresbury Laboratory, Keckwick Ln,
Daresbury WA4 4AD, United Kingdom, and
High Performance Computing Center Stuttgart, Nobelstr. 19, 70569 Stuttgart, Germany*

This document serves as a placeholder for future addenda to the FOUST 2021 workshop proceedings paper on mereosemiotics [1].

Acknowledgment. This work was funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) through the National Research Data Infrastructure for Catalysis-Related Sciences (NFDI4-Cat), DFG project no. 441926934, within the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) programme of the Joint Science Conference (GWK). It was facilitated by activities of the Innovation Centre for Process Data Technology (Inprodat e.V.), Kaiserslautern. Discussions on Metadata4Ing within NFDI4Ing, DFG project no. 442146713, are acknowledged.

References

- [1] M.T. Horsch, Mereosemiotics: Parts and signs, in: *Proceedings of JOWO 2021 (FOUST 2021)*, to appear, CEUR-WS, Aachen, 2021, preprint doi:10.5281/zenodo.4849611.